

Deliverable D1.4 ELIXIR Best Practices recommendations

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¹<https://elixir-europe.org/intranet/data-management-network/members>

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1. Executive Summary

The scope of this deliverable was to provide final best practice recommendations incorporating use of data brokering, business models and pan-European operations, with the aim of capturing, collating, and disseminating the collective research data management (RDM) expertise that resides across the ELIXIR member Nodes.

The data management guidelines aim to promote knowledge sharing and capacity building among the member Nodes, as well as harmonising the guidance across Nodes, while at the same time taking the varying local circumstances at different ELIXIR Nodes into account. The best practice content has been a deeply integrated effort by many partners in most of the Nodes through the work of WP1, WP2, WP3, WP5, WP7, WP8 and WP9, and through the establishment of the Data Management Network. Through the strong position of the RDMkit information resource as a major authority source of life science RDM knowledge, it was also possible to engage contributors beyond those that were participating in the CONVERGE project.

Establishing services to broker data submissions is an effective way to facilitate the flow of FAIR data from life science research to Core Data Resources (CDR), ELIXIR Deposition Databases (EDD) and ELIXIR Community data resources. With the aim to explore existing practice and develop models around brokering data (including the tools, services and training around this) to specific ELIXIR Deposition Resources, three main brokering explorations have been investigated.

The discipline of data stewardship is a relatively new one that will become increasingly more important over time. Data management support services will have to operate for the foreseeable future, and consequently the means by which e.g. an ELIXIR Node can provide sustainable long-term services needs to be explored. To this end, surveys have been conducted to scope the current business model landscape, and put together as a Business Model Catalog to serve as inspiration for sustaining node service operations for data management. Existing business models that were currently implemented by the ELIXIR Nodes, as well as current levels of data management service provisioning, have been reviewed to investigate long-term sustainability strategies for supporting the provision of data management/data stewardship services.

To encourage harmonisation in the way ELIXIR Nodes provide data management support to research projects, an operating model for harmonised data management in European projects has been developed as a guide for data managers and data stewards to assist researchers in offering advice on responsible management approaches in life-science domains. The model itself is a set of recommendations and best practices in data management applicable in European projects, guaranteeing an overall harmony in data management practice.

Conclusions:

- A pan-European network of data experts that meets monthly, serving as a conduit for information exchange between individuals in the network and researchers/data stewards within institutions represented by the node. This community of practice can serve future and sustained projects within ELIXIR, with a synergistic international exchange of solutions, thus contributing with training and documenting of best practices even after the project CONVERGE ends.
- A comprehensive collection of best practice guidelines relevant to the life science domain has been developed and refined over the years, and has been made available through the RDMkit

resource that has been designed and established by WP3. The content of the guidelines is presented through several orthogonal entryways – the *Data life cycle*, *Your role*, *Your domain*, *Your tasks*, *Tool assembly*, and *National resources*. The RDMkit has become a major authoritative source of life science RDM knowledge.

- The guidelines have served to help in identifying and prioritising data management training needs and the development of training material.
- Contributions of content have come from a large number of Nodes and experts, including members not only in WP1, but also WP2, WP3, WP5, WP7, WP8 and WP9, from the broader Data Management Network, as well as experts outside of ELIXIR.
- Content has been generated in a crowdsourcing manner, both during hackathons and contentathons organised in topic-specific focus groups. This process has sparked discussions that in themselves are an important part of the knowledge-sharing and capacity building process and the results from these discussions are available in an accessible manner in the RDMkit.
- Through WP1 T1.2, extensive discussions have been had to devise brokering models for a variety of different life science groups. This has allowed valuable insight into the needs of those who openly share / would like to openly share data on a large-scale. These discussions also benefit the target repositories through feedback as to how their services can be improved.
- Ultimately, T1.2 highlights a brokering landscape, showing a variety of ways that data brokering can be performed, the different roles brokers can take on, and the ways in which these can benefit the scientific community (e.g. by enhancing data sharing and/or metadata quality).
- Most Nodes are in an establishment phase in their data management operations with frequent lack of established business models, and services delivery are only supported by public subsidisation in almost all the Nodes.
- Nodes are moving towards the exploration of new sustainability strategies and models where part of the costs are recovered from final users.
- A single one-size-fit-all sustainability strategy can not be advocated for all Nodes. The implemented business model strategies can be grouped according to the gradient of public subsidisation and user/customer contribution under three business models (in the so called Business Model Catalog): Free, Freemium and Pay per use.
- A harmonised operating model for providing data management support to projects has been designed, that follows these steps: i) Establishment of Data Expert Network, ii) Implementation of Data Life Cycle into the operating model, iii) Application of Best Practices reflected in RDMkit, iv) Mapping of supporting IT infrastructure and computational resources availability and utilisation, and v) Funding model of the data management as an ELIXIR Service.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	Yes
Key Result 1.2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	Yes
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	Yes
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	Yes
Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	Yes
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	No
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	Yes
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to	Yes

integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	Yes
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	Yes
Key Result 3.4: Enable 'FAIR at source' practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	Yes
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	No
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	No
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	No
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	No
Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.	No

3. Introduction

The scope of this deliverable was to provide final best practice recommendations incorporating use of data brokering, business models and pan-European operations, with the aim of capturing, collating, and disseminating the collective research data management (RDM) expertise that resides across the ELIXIR member Nodes. Since the growth and diversity of datasets and platforms have steadily increased in the last decade, the need for data to be better managed becomes highly important. Advancing the understanding of life science and translating data resources into societal benefits and economic growth in the long run requires that all components follow the FAIR principles. However, there is a large unmet need for Data Management capacity building, guidance and harmonisation in the life-sciences to achieve this. In this context, ELIXIR is uniquely placed to coordinate national-level expertise in terms of life-science data management in Europe. However, it should be pointed out that the level of expertise and capacity is not uniformly spread across the Nodes, nor is the coverage of expertise in the various areas of data management. There is a need for capacity building, whereby all Nodes contribute part of the knowledge, as well as to learn from others. The ELIXIR-CONVERGE project has established an ELIXIR Data Management Network that gathers the data management expertise existing in the member Nodes. This deliverable is a comprehensive collection of the data management practice guidelines expertise that reside within the Data Management Network.

The data management guidelines aim to promote knowledge sharing and capacity building among the member Nodes, as well as harmonising the guidance across Nodes, while at the same time taking the varying local circumstances at different ELIXIR Nodes into account. The guidelines should also help in identifying and prioritising data management training needs and the development of training material. Finally, the guidelines should highlight how ELIXIR services and resources can address data management challenges for the wider life science research community.

The work to establish best practice guidelines to a great extent interacts with the work performed in the working groups *WP2 Training*, *WP3 Toolkit*, *WP5 Demonstrators*, *WP7 Federated European Genome-phenome Archives for transnational access of COVID-19 host data*, *WP8 European COVID-19 Data Platform*, and *WP9 Mobilisation of SARS-CoV-2 variant surveillance data*. This cross-fertilisation often implicated the same individuals. Expert knowledge from WP1, WP2, WP5, WP7, WP8 and WP9 was brought together to establish the best practice guidelines *content*, and the WP3 RDMkit web resource offers a *structure* and a *platform* to disseminate the content of these guidelines.

Establishing services to broker data submissions is an effective way to facilitate the flow of FAIR data from life science research to Core Data Resources (CDR), ELIXIR Deposition Databases (EDD) and ELIXIR Community data resources. Data brokering also benefits the broker, providing recognition and leverage for large-scale data coordination projects. Operating such services is however not straightforward, and can be done on several different levels of operational complexity. The work done aims to investigate and explore different models and scenarios for doing data brokering to facilitate future best practices in this area.

To encourage harmonisation in the way ELIXIR Nodes provide data management support to research projects, an operating model for harmonised data management in European projects has been developed as a guide for data managers and data stewards to assist researchers in offering advice on responsible management approaches in life-science domains. The model itself is a set of

recommendations and best practices in data management applicable in European projects, guaranteeing an overall harmony in data management practice.

The discipline of data stewardship is a relatively new one that will become increasingly more important over time. Data management support services will have to operate for the foreseeable future, and consequently the means by which e.g. an ELIXIR Node can provide sustainable long-term services needs to be explored. To this end, surveys have been conducted to scope the current business model landscape, and put together a Business Model Catalog to serve as inspiration for sustaining node service operations for data management.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Collating data management best practice content

A *Best practice guidelines working group* was formed by a subset of members from the Data Management Coordinators group², that over time has consisted of representatives from ELIXIR-BE, ELIXIR-CZ, ELIXIR-FR, ELIXIR-NL, ELIXIR-NO, ELIXIR-PT, and ELIXIR-SE, to coordinate the work of establishing the best practice guidelines. The group has had regular meetings throughout the project. The initial work was focused on defining the scope, target audience and format of dissemination for this first version of the best practice guidelines. Given that the finer details of data management guidelines are highly dependent on the local situation, it was decided that the scope should be limited to general principles that would be applicable regardless of the environment in which a potential reader would be working. Researchers and the research-supporting *Data Steward* role were selected as the primary focus audience for the guideline content. The RDMkit portal developed by WP3 was used as the platform for disseminating the best practice guidelines content. To oversee quality and coherence of the multi-party contributions, WP3 established an editorial board for the RDMkit. The RDMkit and the editorial processes are described in more detail in *D3.1 Assembled starter toolkit*³.

The initial best practice guidelines content has been collected in a crowdsourcing manner by the members of WP1 and the broader Data Management Network⁴, in large parts through the “Hackathons” and “Contentathons” (events for groups of people to meet up and collaboratively create code and content) organised by WP3. After the initial content creation, the Best practice guidelines working group has coordinated the WP1 contributed expansion of the content materials. Suggestions for content additions was prioritised in collaboration with the RDMkit editorial board. Prioritised topics were tackled by forming short-lived focus groups consisting of contributors with expert knowledge, both from within and outside ELIXIR. Individual ELIXIR Nodes, through the WP1 members, have also contributed guidelines content based on the different national circumstances on the *National resources* pages. Updates on progress have been reported on the regular monthly meetings of the Data Management Network.

WP2 has identified existing training courses and resources in ELIXIR’s Training Portal TeSS⁵, and mapped them with the relevant RDMkit pages so that both resources, TeSS and RDMkit, are effectively linked.

²<https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/converge/wp1/dm-coordinators>

³https://zenodo.org/record/4501634#.YBweuo_7T0o

⁴<https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/converge/wp1/dm-network>

⁵<https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>

As described in *D3.2 Toolkit extension based on first wave demonstrators*⁶, WP3 also engaged the different demonstrators of WP5, as well as infrastructures and communities outside of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project, to create content for different science domains and tool assemblies. Furthermore, the later addition WPs (WP7, WP8 and WP9), that were established through the project financial uplift due to the COVID-19 pandemic, have also contributed best practice content to the RDMkit.

The work of WP1, WP2, WP3, WP5, WP7, WP8 and WP9 to produce this resource has been a deeply integrated effort, as many people are involved in several WPs. Further, members across these WPs have been coordinating content updates and established links between the RDMkit and the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) ELIXIR Knowledge model, as well as links between RDMkit and the FAIR Cookbook⁷, and RDMkit and FAIRsharing⁸, on top of the links with TeSS mentioned above. This work is further described in *D3.3 Single entry-point portal for the toolkit for all stakeholders*⁹.

4.2 Data brokering to deposition databases

Data brokering to ELIXIR repositories appears in several CONVERGE Work packages, namely WP1 (T1.2) and WP9 (T9.1), with both tasks being led by EMBL-EBI. WP9 focuses on SARS-CoV-2 data brokering, while WP1 concerns other data types, also going beyond nucleotide sequencing data.

For WP1, the aim of T1.2 was to explore existing practice and develop models around brokering data (including the tools, services and training around this) to specific ELIXIR Deposition Resources. We also aimed to document and resolve best practice, and where appropriate, develop prototypes based on these models.

To approach this task, an initial kick-off meeting with various resources (such as the ENA, UniProt, LipidMaps) and ELIXIR Nodes, was organised to better understand how they support researchers and engage with other resources. Next, we invited interested groups to submit brokering 'exploration proposals' through a survey. These were named as proposals because the goal is to explore, not to build, as T1.2 has little budget assigned to it. We received 5 responses from across ELIXIR Nodes and projects, including: Collaborative Open Plant Omics (COPO), Online Resource for Community Annotation of Eukaryotes (ORCAE), the FAIRDOME consortium (providing the FAIRDOME-SEEK research data management platform), LIPID MAPS (Lipid data platform) and the SciLifeLab Data Centre in Sweden.

We engaged in further meetings with these 5 groups to discuss their proposals in more detail in order to, e.g. understand destination repositories, potential mechanisms of brokering, and identifying synergies with other groups. From this, 3 main brokering explorations were followed through to a mature stage – these are:

1. Metadata brokering from FAIRDOME-SEEK's research data management platform to the ENA and other repositories
2. Brokering of cryoEM data from SciLifeLab's Infrastructure Unit to Electron Microscopy Archive (and protein databases)

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5139897>

⁷ <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org>

⁸ <https://fairsharing.org>

⁹

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1IY4CSoaW2ROkIQK8AH9r0muWlj55sPmq7DrO9DDNJeo/edit#heading=h.khrm57wwg4r>

3. Interarchive brokering (and curation) of primarily lipid data between MetaboLights, ChEBI and LIPID MAPS

With regards to dissemination activities, FAIRDOM-SEEK's brokering proposal was accepted as a project for the 2022 ELIXIR Biohackathon.

Data brokering in WP9 on the other hand, focused on SARS-CoV-2 data. T9.1 aimed to strengthen support for national brokers of this data into the ENA and COVID-19 Data Portal, including helpdesk support, and providing SARS-CoV-2 data submission tools for brokers.

There is some overlap in the network of brokers in WP9 and WP1 (e.g. ELIXIR Belgium were also involved in submission of SARS-CoV-2 data to the ENA), and meetings with public health authorities/national infrastructures to set up COVID data brokering streams in WP9, have helped the ENA better understand the needs of its brokers as well as the legal and ethical considerations of this set up, which also apply to WP1.

Furthermore, in September 2022, a collaborative ELIXIR CONVERGE Data Brokering Workshop was organised, involving WP1, 8 and 9. The goal of this workshop was to define what data brokering is and cover different examples of how this can be performed, with different data types and in different contexts (including SARS-CoV-2). A breakout session on developing a pathogen maturity model for data brokers was also organised as part of this.

4.3 Business models

Existing business models that were currently implemented by the ELIXIR Nodes were reviewed to investigate long-term sustainability strategies for supporting the provision of data management/data stewardship services.

Data collection about business models was performed by means of on-line surveys and interviews with ELIXIR Nodes, investigating how DM/DS services are delivered in individual countries and how they are financially supported. The current investigation was performed at different time points along the implementation of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE action, allowing the sketching of an analysis of the evolution of the delivered services, and their financial sustainability in a two years time frame.

As the ELIXIR Nodes are differently structured, a single one-size-fit-all sustainability strategy can not be advocated. Hence a catalogue of fact sheets for all the approaches, different from the full public subsidisation was generated: the so called, Business Models Catalog. The catalogue characterises the implemented sustainability strategies under three (plus one) business models: Free, Freemium, Pay per use (Pay per use +).

The complete outcomes on business models investigation is described in *D1.2 Survey of business models*¹⁰.

4.4 Harmonised operating model

The harmonised model defines a procedure to provide data management support services at all ELIXIR Nodes based on research institutions/teams/individual requirements and ELIXIR preparedness to lead, help, or supervise the process. The model background was set by already existing requirements on data management plans for projects funded by the EU's research and

¹⁰<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6344131>

innovation framework programme Horizon Europe in which the preparation of data management plans became mandatory, as well as by user experience. The strategy was based on interconnection of work-packages of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project, but primarily relied on Tasks of WP1. It became obvious that WP3 and the establishment of RDMkit naturally integrated best practices and know-how resulting from tasks of WP1, WP2, WP5, WP7, WP8 and WP9. Nevertheless, the model creation was anticipated as a linear procedure composed of defined steps which are mutually harmonizable and reflects both general and country specific requirements on the data management process.

The central strategy for the harmonised operating model was based on the following steps: i) Establishment of Data Expert Network, ii) Implementation of Data Life Cycle into the operating model, iii) Application of Best Practices reflected in RDMkit, iv) Mapping of supporting IT infrastructure and computational resources availability and utilisation, and v) Funding model of the data management as an ELIXIR Service.

The work on a harmonised operating model is described in more detail in *D1.3 A pan-European model for data management in life sciences*¹¹.

5. Results

5.1 Best practice content

In close collaboration with WP2, WP3, WP5, members of WP1 and the broader Data Management Network have analysed the types of practices and other content, such as ELIXIR services that have a role in data management, that need to be captured in the RDMkit resource. They have contributed to establish the templates used to create the content relative to the different aspects of data management.

Content has been provided by many partners in most of the Nodes, and through the establishment of the Data Management Network. Through the strong position of the RDMkit information resource as a major authority source of life science RDM knowledge, it was also possible to engage contributors beyond those that were participating in the CONVERGE project.

The RDMkit offers several orthogonal entryways to the data management content – the *Data life cycle*, *Your role*, *Your domain*, *Your tasks*, *Tool assembly*, and *National resources*. The RDMkit is described in more detail in *D3.1 Assembled starter toolkit*¹².

- The *Data life cycle* pages provide a high-level description of the importance of, and considerations for, good data management practices during the different phases of the data life cycle. These pages then refer to relevant *Your tasks* pages for more in-depth information.
- The *Your role* pages provide descriptions of different roles, and the tasks, considerations, resources and training related to those roles regarding research data management.
- The *Your domain* pages captures data management best practice approaches for different domains in the life sciences.
- The *Your tasks* pages describe particular data management issues in more detail, and also refer to relevant tools and resources to address the problem. These recommendations highlight

¹¹ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1rc8KK85W1z-3lfhMDNqz15eGI3PVQslyRxxDkizQfzg/edit?usp=sharing>

¹² https://zenodo.org/record/4501634#.YBweuo_7T0o

existing high-quality resources, such as for example those assigned to the ELIXIR Deposition Databases list, as well as to established ELIXIR services.

- The *Tool assembly* pages showcase examples of combining tools to solve data management tasks across several steps in the data life cycle.
- The *National resources* pages describe existing national policies, guidelines, and solutions for different countries.

On all pages, tools and training resources that are relevant for the particular topics are listed, and the full lists of these are also listed on separate overview pages for tools and training. An overview of the current content of the pages in the different sections of the RDMkit is summarised in *Table 1*.

An important aspect of the work done, that might not be apparent from the output generated, but merits mention, is the value of the process of the collective discussions generated by the various viewpoints and backgrounds of the participants. It is this rich and open exchange that eventually led to the generation of the content presented here. The discussions themselves are an important part of working towards a shared language and knowledge base of harmonised best practice guidelines for the ELIXIR Data Management Network.

Table 1. Content overview of RDMkit pages

Data life cycle ¹³	
Planning	Describes the aims and benefits of data management planning, and Data Management Plans (DMPs).
Collecting	Describes the importance of practices to ensure data quality and capturing provenance.
Processing	Describes practices for preparing data for analysis, such as harmonizing data formats, file structure, and applying documentation and metadata standards.
Analysing	Focuses on structuring data, and documenting data and analysis.
Preserving	Outlines practices and considerations for preserving the data long term.
Sharing	Describes the reasons and considerations to be addressed to make the data known and available to the research community and society at large, according to the FAIR principles.
Reusing	Describes practices to employ to ensure quality and interoperability when reusing data.
Your role ¹⁴	
Researcher	Presents the view of a researcher, that with the help of the Data Steward Research, focuses on best practices in RDM and in writing Data Management Plans.
Data Steward: policy	Focuses on the role of providing policy development and the implementation of research data management in their institution.
Data Steward: research	Describes the role of Data Stewards that provide data management support and advice to researchers in their institution and ensures the quality of their

¹³ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/data_life_cycle

¹⁴ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/your_role

	data management plans.
Data Steward: infrastructure	Focuses on the role of ensuring compliance between data infrastructure and RDM policies.
Your domain¹⁵	
Bioimaging data	Best practices for (meta)data standards, (meta)data collection and publication/archiving of bioimaging data.
Biomolecular simulation data	Storing and sharing recommendations for biomolecular simulation data.
Epitranscriptome data	Guidelines for collecting, processing/analysing, and preserving/sharing epitranscriptomic data.
Human data	Outlines ethical, legal, and information security considerations for working with human data throughout the data life cycle.
Intrinsically disordered proteins	Guidelines for annotating and curating intrinsically disordered protein experiments for FAIRness.
Marine metagenomics	Describes metadata standards management and tools/resources for analysing marine metagenomics data.
Microbial biotechnology	Guidelines for data management considerations for the Design-Build-Test-Learn (DBTL) cycle of microbial biotechnology experiments.
Plant sciences	Best practices for plant sciences data management challenges - materials, phenotyping and genotyping metadata collection and sharing.
Proteomics	Describes standard formats, processing/analysing and preserving/sharing of FAIR proteomics data.
Rare disease data	Data management guidelines for handling rare disease data and metadata throughout the data life cycle.
Structural bioinformatics	Storing and sharing recommendations for structure predictions of biological macromolecules.
Toxicology data	Guidelines for managing toxicology data from <i>in vitro</i> assays, animal assays, human assays and ecotoxicology studies.
Your tasks¹⁶	
Compliance monitoring	Focuses on how to document and monitor that legal obligations and policies are being adhered to.
Data analysis	Describes how to ensure reproducibility of analyses performed.
Data brokering	Describes the data broker role, and what to consider when collecting and sharing data in repositories on behalf of data producers.
Data management coordination	Describes considerations and solutions on how to organise, execute and sustain data management in collaborative projects.

¹⁵ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/your_domain

¹⁶ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/your_tasks

Data management plan	Recommendations for DMP content, templates and solutions.
Data organisation	Describes good practices for file naming, file and folder organisation, and version control.
Data protection	Describes the issues to be considered when handling personal data under the GDPR.
Data provenance	Describes how to best record data provenance information.
Data publication	Guidance on how to select suitable repositories for data publishing.
Data quality	Describes factors affecting data quality, and solutions to help ensure data quality.
Data storage	Describes different options for data storage during different stages of the data life cycle.
Data transfer	Focuses on solutions and considerations to transfer large data files.
Documentation and metadata	Describes how to document data, and solutions for finding suitable metadata standards and ontologies to describe data.
Existing data	Focuses on data reuse, how to find existing data and what to consider before reusing the data.
Identifiers	Describes how unique identifiers should be used during data collection as well as when publishing data.
Licensing	Guidance on how to select licences for reuse of data and code, to promote reusability.
Machine actionability	Describes motivations and considerations for making data and metadata retrievable, readable and interpretable by computers.
Sensitive data	Guidance on determining if data is sensitive (with focus on personal data) and how to de-identify data.
Tool assembly¹⁷	
COVID-19 Data Portal	A data portal that brings together and continuously updates relevant COVID-19 datasets from a breadth of analytical platforms.
CSC	The services, tools and software for managing research data throughout the project life cycle provided by CSC – IT Center for Science and ELIXIR Finland.
Galaxy	The Galaxy open-source platform for FAIR data analysis.
IFB	The French national bioinformatics environment, consisting of IT infrastructure, software and training.
Marine Metagenomics	The Norwegian tool assembly for marine metagenomics.
NeLS	The Norwegian e-Infrastructure for Life Sciences (NeLS) that provides integrated tools necessary for Data Management.
OMERO	A software platform for managing, sharing and analysing imaging data.
Plant Genomics	A toolkit for managing plant genomics and genotyping data throughout their

¹⁷ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/tool_assembly

	life cycle.
Plant Phenomics	A tool assembly covering the whole life cycle of experimental plant phenotyping data.
TransMed	A data and computing tool assembly for clinical and translational projects, provided by ELIXIR Luxembourg.
TSD	A secure compute environment for sensitive data.
XNAT-PIC	XNAT for Preclinical Imaging Centers (XNAT-PIC) consists of a set of tools to store, process and share preclinical imaging studies.
National resources¹⁸	
Multiple national pages	Country-specific information resources such as local funding agencies and research councils, and information on local policies for open science, national regulations on data ethics, and domain-specific infrastructures and tools.

5.2 Data brokering to deposition databases

Through several meetings and discussion, models describing the mechanism of data brokering were devised for each of the three brokering groups:

1. Metadata brokering from FAIRDOM-SEEK’s research data management platform to the ENA and other repositories

Figure 1. Overview of metadata brokering model from Datahub (which utilises the FAIRDOM-SEEK software) to multiple ELIXIR resources

¹⁸ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/national_resources

Datahub is a research data and metadata management platform, which utilises the FAIRDOME-SEEK software, and is currently in development by ELIXIR Belgium together with the FAIRDOME consortium. Datahub exports data in ISA-JSON file format, containing information about the study, source material, derived samples and performed experimental techniques, in a single file. This metadata can be brokered into several ELIXIR deposition databases, such as ENA, Array Express, Biosamples, PRIDE, etc. While ISA-JSON better reflects the nature of scientific projects, it is not widely accepted for submission by such ELIXIR deposition repositories, which have largely heterogeneous data submission methods.

As a result of the successful ELIXIR Biohackathon 2022, a prototype ISA-JSON converter tool was developed, which converts ISA-JSON into XML format, suitable for ENA and Biosample submission. The code is available on Github¹⁹. To build on this, we would like to engage other ELIXIR repositories to create mappings between metadata fields required by their respective databases, and ISA-JSON fields, in order to allow submissions to other repositories.

A BioHackrXiv paper describing the outcomes of the Biohackathon and future work in more detail is planned to be submitted early 2023.

2. Brokering of cryoEM data from SciLifeLab's Infrastructure Unit to Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive (and protein databases)

Figure 2. Overview of cryo-EM brokering model from SciLifeLab to EMPIAR (Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive), PDBe (Protein Data Bank in Europe) and EMDB (Electron Microscopy Data Bank)

The SciLifeLab brokering use case is at an earlier stage, and involves brokering cryogenic electron microscopy data (e.g. 3D molecular structure, 2D electron microscopy maps and images) from their national cryo-EM facility, to EMPIAR, EMDB and PDBe repositories, in response to the growing volume of this data type, and to make it publicly accessible. A temporary 'staging area' as part of

¹⁹ <https://github.com/elixir-europe/biohackathon-projects-2022/tree/main/27/ISASRAProject27>

SciLifeLab's infrastructure is a key feature of this model, as submission of a complete cryo-EM dataset is a step-wise process, with e.g. EMPIAR accepting data only once the underlying elements have become public in the remaining two archives.

While the temporary staging area is currently being developed in SciLifeLab, this brokering model aims to boost Swedish cryo-EM data submissions to the global scientific community.

3. Interarchive brokering (and curation) of primarily lipid data between MetaboLights, ChEBI and LIPID MAPS

Figure 3. Overview of Lipid inter-archive brokering model, where data is 'moved' between MetaboLights, LIPID MAPS and ChEBI (Chemical Entities of Biological Interest) databases

LIPID MAPS is a major global resource in the lipidomics domain, supporting researchers with data deposition, tools for analysis and lipid drawing, as well as a lipid encyclopaedia.

Unlike the first two models, which involve brokering data from a user submission platform to target repositories, this model is not only at the earliest stage, but aims to broker data *between* repositories, namely: LIPID MAPS, ChEBI and MetaboLights, and cross-reference the lipid, metabolite and chemical structure data across these databases. Lipid curation using ChEBI and MetaboLights data is an additional element of this task, as lipids are often not well characterised and can be mismatched to a database record. As part of future work in this task, workflows and pipelines will need to be designed/enhanced.

Currently a detailed task list has been defined for this brokering exploration, and relevant groups are exploring funding beyond ELIXIR CONVERGE to achieve this. If implemented, this model would be another example to showcase improved interoperability across ELIXIR resources.

Regarding data brokering in general, best practice considerations and solutions have been collated and made available as a *Your tasks* page in the RDMkit through work carried out in *WP9 Mobilisation of SARS-CoV-2 variant surveillance data*²⁰.

²⁰ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/data_brokering

5.3 Business models

At the end of the investigation, only a slight increase of the number of Nodes delivering DM/DS services could be observed. However, the collected evidence suggests that the quality of provided services improved, reflecting an increased maturity of the Nodes in this field. The investigation highlighted how Nodes providing dedicated IT infrastructure for data management have more than doubled in less than 2 years, again suggesting a maturity boost in the provision of DM/DS services by several Nodes.

The business models investigation revealed that data management services delivery, in the current implementations, is only supported by public subsidisation in almost all the Nodes. Funds supporting DM/DS services usually come from a mix of public grants, provided by the local institution, national public funders and European Union/European Commission funded projects. In almost one third of cases, Nodes are moving towards the exploration of new sustainability strategies and models where part of the costs are recovered from final users.

Considering the gradient of public subsidisation and user/customer contribution, the implemented sustainability strategies were characterised under three (plus one) business models: *Free*, *Freemium*, *Pay per use* (*Pay per use +*). These alternative funding strategies (other than the full public subsidisation implemented by the Nodes) are defined in the Business Model Catalog (see D1.2 Survey of business models, Appendix I).

Although a growing number of Nodes are moving towards the implementation of such business models, the investigation highlights how these strategies for most of the cases can be considered only experimental, and so far, in several cases transactions are only virtual and cost recovery almost never happens in full.

In spite of DM/DS services being supported by temporary grants, in the vast majority of cases the Nodes estimate that the DM/DS services are “Likely to be sustainable” for the future time frame, reflecting an optimistic sentiment about the services financial sustainability, services which are in turn expected to keep growing in the future.

5.4 Harmonised operating model

Taking into account the complexity of providing data management services, as well as their desired harmonisation, it is beneficial to provide a procedure guaranteeing a seamless connection of the recommended particular steps and the application of know-how and tools developed during the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project. The model procedure consists of several consecutive steps while expecting readiness of the national environment towards data management and, if applicable, also the utilisation of the ELIXIR developed strategies, tools and resources:

Step 1) Expert network and national data management hubs;

It is fully based on the outcome of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE, WP1, Task 1.1, where the identification of personnel authorities as well as scientific centres providing assistance in the Data Management is documented.

Step 2) Consulting services to analyse project plans and data stewardship strategies;

Involvement of key experts and trained personnels will guarantee that the data management plans of projects are aligned with project plans according to the best practices and national requirements. The creation of data management plans reflects complexity of the project and ELIXIR recommended tools for data management plan guarantees its utilisation.

Step 3) Recommended ELIXIR data management tools;

It is strongly recommended to researchers with limited knowledge of data management as well as for those with extended skills to consult RDMkit²¹. This will guarantee easy access to a curated collection of research data management guidelines, best practices, tools, and services.

Step 4) Data storage, data access, open science;

A key element in the data management planning is the localization of IT resources for production and post-production phases defined by the *Data life cycle*²². If provided by an infrastructure dealing with data archiving or providing data storage capacity, a business model should be in place. If the data storage (e.g. deposition databases for long-term storage recommended by ELIXIR) and data provision are fully supported by the project, the detailed cost must be provided and the requirements of a provider must be fulfilled. In the current situation, most of the specialised IT services are outsourced or, based on the previously mentioned paid services, offered by specialised infrastructure. According to the project plan, a detailed process towards the data access should be described with all applicable licence conditions and data policy depending on a character of the data generated by the project. A possible overlap with EOSC activities shall be also provided.

Step 5) Activity based funding approach of data management and financial security;

The current situation calls for a more systematic approach for secured funding, given the fact that the financial resources for data management/data stewardship are heterogeneous. Most of the ELIXIR Nodes rely on a portfolio of such resources. Nevertheless, they need to minimise risk and formulate risk management for cases when some of the resources will become unavailable in the future. So far, there is no accurate financial analysis of the current revenues and expenditures. The trend towards a model where costs are charged to the end users is evident.

There is a prospective solution that DM/DS services can be provided in a harmonised way by a research infrastructure including financial resources. In the life-science fields, it is ELIXIR whose experience and instant solution for DM/DS are of the highest quality, and the sustainability of the infrastructure is the natural solution to the problem. Most of the national ELIXIR infrastructures are on the national roadmaps and their development and financial support has a long-term character.

6. Conclusions

- A pan-European network of data experts that meets monthly, serving as a conduit for information exchange between individuals in the network and researchers/data stewards within institutions represented by the node. This community of practice can serve future and sustained projects within ELIXIR, with a synergistic international exchange of solutions, thus

²¹ <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org>

²² https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/data_life_cycle

contributing with training and documenting of best practices even after the project CONVERGE ends.

- A comprehensive collection of best practice guidelines relevant to the life science domain has been developed and refined over the years, and has been made available through the RDMkit resource that has been designed and established by WP3. The content of the guidelines is presented through several orthogonal entryways – the *Data life cycle*, *Your role*, *Your domain*, *Your tasks*, *Tool assembly*, and *National resources*. The RDMkit has become a major authoritative source of life science RDM knowledge.
- The guidelines have served to help in identifying and prioritising data management training needs and the development of training material.
- Contributions of content have come from a large number of Nodes and experts, including members not only in WP1, but also WP2, WP3, WP5, WP7, WP8 and WP9, from the broader Data Management Network, as well as experts outside of ELIXIR.
- Content has been generated in a crowdsourcing manner, both during hackathons and contentathons organised in topic-specific focus groups. This process has sparked discussions that in themselves are an important part of the knowledge-sharing and capacity building process and the results from these discussions are available in an accessible manner in the RDMkit.
- Through WP1 T1.2 extensive discussions have been had to devise brokering models for a variety of different life science groups. This has allowed obtaining valuable insight into the needs of those who openly share / would like to openly share data on a large-scale. These discussions also benefit the target repositories through feedback as to how their services can be improved.
- Ultimately T1.2 highlights a brokering landscape, showing a variety of ways that data brokering can be performed, the different roles brokers can take on, and the ways in which these can benefit the scientific community (e.g. by enhancing data sharing and/or metadata quality).
- Most Nodes are in an establishment phase in their data management operations with frequent lack of established business models, and services delivery are only supported by public subsidisation in almost all the Nodes.
- Nodes are moving towards the exploration of new sustainability strategies and models where part of the costs are recovered from final users.
- A single one-size-fit-all sustainability strategy can not be advocated for all Nodes. The implemented business model strategies can be grouped according to the gradient of public subsidisation and user/customer contribution under three business models (in the so called Business Model Catalog): Free, Freemium and Pay per use.
- A harmonised operating model for providing data management support to projects has been designed, that follows these steps: i) Establishment of Data Expert Network, ii) Implementation of Data Life Cycle into the operating model, iii) Application of Best Practices reflected in RDMkit, iv) Mapping of supporting IT infrastructure and computational resources availability and utilisation, and v) Funding model of the data management as an ELIXIR Service.

7. Impact

At this point in time, the impact of the work done is well received. The RDMkit as a knowledge base

has become a *de facto* major authoritative source of information regarding DM/DS in the life sciences. Since 2021, the European Commission refers to the RDMkit in their recommendations in data management planning for the projects. The US National Institute of Health has engaged in the coordination of knowledge content. National funder guidelines, e.g. Norway, recommend the RDMkit as a best practice resource. This work has resulted in a comprehensive body of knowledge that will allow researchers and data management professionals to be able to learn and apply good data management practices in the life science domain. Researchers and data stewards developing DMPs will be able to build upon the best practices descriptions as background material. ELIXIR service providers will be able to ensure that their services are discoverable by data managers and researchers who can make use of them to enable and facilitate their work. The ELIXIR data managers in the Data Management Network will be able to use the RDMkit to refer to well written descriptions of best practices and tool assemblies. This contributes towards the ELIXIR-CONVERGE Key Results 1.1, 1.2, 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3. The work covers the knowledge body of data management practices that are relevant to the life science domain, and thus provides a base on which to establish a training and capacity building programme. In this, it also contributes to Key Results 2.1 and 2.3.

The data brokering explorations as part of T1.2 have brought forward important, wider discussions surrounding data brokering, including how it can be defined, performed, and the roles of brokers and target repositories. Indeed this drove the organisation of the Data Brokering Workshop in September 2022, and we hope to continue some of these discussions even beyond ELIXIR-CONVERGE. Additionally, while each brokering model aims to enhance the quality and movement of data to specific ELIXIR repositories, the FAIRDOM exploration arguably has the potential to be most impactful, as it aims more broadly to improve the way multi-omics data can be accepted by such repositories.

The business models investigation provided the opportunity for the Nodes to dedicate time for focusing on the current and future sustainability strategies for the delivery of DM/DS services. It allowed the Nodes to generate a clear picture of how DM/DS services are coordinated within the Country, and sketch a fair picture of the real future services sustainability. An impact is expected in the mid-term future for Nodes where service provision is rapidly growing in maturity via an alignment to the business models proposed in the Business Model Catalog. It also helped in designing a harmonised operating model for data management within ELIXIR. This contributes towards Key Results 1.3 and 1.4.

8. Next Steps

The body of knowledge that has been collated through this effort is not an endpoint in itself, but something that will have to be continuously updated and expanded over time.

The DM best practice guidelines, brokering explorations, business model inventory and harmonised operation model description has built a foundation for the ELIXIR Nodes to offer DM services. However, there is still great heterogeneity in capability among the different nodes, and a need for further capacity building and means of sustaining those DM services to their local communities. Data brokering models, as well as possible business models must be developed further. Developing maturity models for various aspects of providing services, e.g. data brokering to deposition databases, and node DM services operations more generally, can be used to drive that work. Node

DM service operation knowledge should also be collated into a “Data management services providers knowledge handbook”.

More work needs to be done to incorporate the sustainability solutions captured in the Business Model Catalog, as well as the suggested harmonised operating model, into the strategies of the ELIXIR Nodes. A possible way forward could be to create a DM operations maturity model based on this work, to aid and guide the ELIXIR Nodes in their ambitions to create sustainable and harmonised DM services.

The RDMkit is part of, and integrated with, a larger “RDM Knowledge ecosystem” of resources. The knowledge management coordination of these resources, as well as the DM Network of people and the Training capabilities established in the project, need to find a sustainable structure within the ELIXIR organisation going forward. Plans to establish this structure in the form of an ELIXIR Community are currently being worked on.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

Not applicable

